

**EFFECT OF BLENDED LEARNING ON ACHIEVEMENT AND
ATTITUDE OF PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS TOWARDS
EDUCATIONAL PSYCHOLOGY**

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Abstract

Blended learning (b-learning) is considered as the dominant instructional model in education. This paper investigates the effectiveness and uses of a blended learning in educational psychology. It is aimed at determining the significant predictors of blended learning effectiveness taking as independent variables and achievement and attitude as dependent variables. The study was an experimental one. The specific design used was a Quasi experimental design i.e., Pre-test-Post-test non equivalent group design for studying the effect of blended learning on the achievement and attitude of prospective teachers towards educational psychology. The experimentation results were used as a measure for performance as an outcome. We administered both groups (experimental and control) of prospective teachers with pre-test on achievement and attitude towards educational psychology in the beginning and then after giving treatment to both the groups we again administered post-test on achievement in educational psychology as well as a test on attitude of prospective teachers towards educational psychology. Statistical hypotheses were tested and statistical analysis results showed that there is significant effect in positive direction of blended learning on achievement and attitude of prospective teachers towards Educational Psychology. According to the stakeholders' views, learning through blended learning led students to think, inquire and explore the subject matter, share their opinions, discuss and appraise others' opinions. Also, it was revealed that students gained different perspectives and were able to think deeply and critically.

Key words: *Blended Learning, ICT, Prospective teachers, Educational Psychology*

Introduction

Blended learning is a pedagogical approach where more than one delivery mode is used to optimize learning outcomes (Singh & Reed,

2001). It is a coherent teaching approach that openly integrates the strengths of face-to-face and online learning (Garrison & Vaughan, 2008). Thus, the mix of traditional teaching with online teaching and interactive forms of classroom training will increase and support student engagement and persistence in class (Throne, 2003). According to McKeachie and Svinicki (2006), blended learning results in positive cognitive outcomes for a wide range of students, including adult learners. Blended learning is an innovative concept that embraces the advantages of both traditional teaching in the classroom and ICT supported learning including both offline learning and online learning. It has scope for collaborative learning; constructivist learning and computer assisted learning (CAI). Blended learning needs rigourous efforts, right attitude, handsome budget and highly motivated teachers and students for its successful implementation. As it incorporates diverse modes so it is complex and organizing it is a difficult task. The educational system at present is in a transition stage. To meet the challenges of expansion and for catering individuals' need it is trying to adopt new technologies and exploring new paths to reach the goal of quality educational opportunities for all, at the same time due to various factors like deficient budgets, lack of facilities, advantages of face to face interactions, it is not completely ready to leave the traditional modes of knowledge transfer. Blended learning is advantageous for students. It provides more scope for communication. Communication cycle is completed in blended learning which is not possible if we follow only traditional approach. Students become more techno savvy and they gain enhanced digital fluency. Also it strengthens professionalism as they develop qualities like self-motivation, self-responsibility, discipline. In our country due to large population the formal school system is not able to provide equal educational opportunities to all, so blended learning will be a good option as it will make the area of educational opportunities wider and education will be able to reach to more children. The technological and scientific development continuously demands the education system to match their pace and correlate with them so that students are able to cope up with the fast changing market. Technology and scientific field are most dynamic and changing at great pace incorporating new innovations so that content transmitted to students have to be revised accordingly. Blended

learning provides varieties of experiences to the students, make them active and they remain in the focus of teaching-learning process due to increased involvement and bearing the responsibility of their learning themselves make students more disciplined. The study here is a try to discover the effect of blended learning in the government and attitude toward educational psychology and the prospective teacher.

Objective

To study the effect of blended learning on the achievement towards educational psychology of prospective teachers.

To study the effect of blended learning on the attitude towards educational psychology of prospective teachers.

Hypotheses

Null hypothesis:1

There is no significant difference between the mean scores in achievement in educational psychology of prospective teachers learning through blended learning and learning through traditional method.

Null hypothesis:2

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of attitude towards educational psychology of prospective teachers learning through blended learning and learning through traditional method.

Methodology

Design

The study was an experimental one. The specific design used was a Quasi experimental design i.e., Pre-test-Post-test non equivalent group design for studying the effect of blended learning on the achievement and attitude of prospective teachers towards

educational psychology. The design of the study has been shown in the following table 1:

Table 1: Design of the study

Random assignment of group	Pre-test	Treatment	Post-test
Experimental group (Intact classroom section-A)	Achievement and Attitude test towards educational psychology	Learning through Blended learning	Achievement and Attitude test towards educational psychology
Control group (Intact classroom section-B)	Achievement and Attitude test towards educational psychology	Learning through traditional method	Achievement and Attitude test towards educational psychology

Population

The population of this study comprised of students studying in B.Ed. colleges of Patna.

Sample

The subject of the study were 100 B.Ed. first year students of St. Xavier's College of Education, Digha, Patna of 2017-2019 batch, strength in class was 100. These students were further divided into two groups of 50 students. One group was experimental and other was control group. Finally as the part of the study 50 prospective teachers in experimental group whereas 48 prospective teachers in control group were taken for study.

Tools

Instructional tool: Blended learning based lesson plan in educational psychology developed by the investigator.

Achievement test on Educational Psychology (ATEP) was developed and validated by the investigator.

Attitude Inventory on Educational Psychology (AIEP) (likert scale) was developed and validated by the investigator.

Procedure of experimentation

In the beginning both the groups (experimental and control) of prospective teachers were administered with pre-test on achievement and attitude towards educational psychology. Then experimental group was taught on one topic of educational

psychology through blended learning method in 4 sessions (periods) and control group was taught the same topic for the same time period by conventional method of teaching. Close observation was kept on students during the classes. After the treatment period spread over two weeks both the groups were again administered with post-test on achievement in educational psychology as well as attitude of prospective teachers towards educational psychology.

Analysis of data

The data collected through the administration of the two tests were analysed through applying required statistical methods, i.e. mean, S.D. and t-test.

Findings

For testing the hypothesis-1 t-test had been done. The mean, standard deviation and t value of the gain scores in achievement in the groups has been shown in the following table:

Table 2: t-test result for hypothesis 1

Groups	N	M	SD	df	t
Experimental	50	6.64	3.14.	96	11.674
Control	48	1.19	0.790		

t value is significant at 0.01 level

It can be seen in table that the number of prospective teachers in experimental and control group was 50 and 48 respectively. Mean of the experimental group was 6.64 and S.D. was 3.141 and the mean of the control group was 1.19 and S.D. was 0.790. The calculated t value was significant at 0.01 level (table value at 0.01 level is 2.73 for 96 df) so the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence it was concluded that there were significant effect of blended learning on the achievement of the prospective teachers in educational psychology than the control group. This outcome can also be seen below:

Fig 1: Mean Gain scores in Achievement in Psychology of experimental and control group

For testing the hypothesis-2 t-test has been done. The mean, standard deviation and t value of the gain scores in attitude towards educational psychology in the groups has been shown below in table3.

Table 3: t-test result for hypothesis 2

Groups	N	M	SD	df	T
Experimental	50	20.30	9.355	96	12.843
Control	48	1.04	6.848		

t value is significant at 0.01 level

It is clearly seen in above table that the number of students in experimental and control group is 50 and 48 respectively. Mean of the experimental group was 6.64 and SD was 9.355 and in the control group mean was 1.04 and SD was 6.848. The calculated t value 12.843 was much higher than the table value (at 0.01 level is 2.73 for 96 df) .

Since t value is significant at 0.01 level, so the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there were significant effect of blended learning on the attitude towards educational psychology among prospective teachers. i.e. this outcome can also be seen below:

Fig 2: Mean scores in Attitude towards Psychology of experimental and control group

Finding on Hypotheses

There is significant effect of blended learning on the achievement in educational psychology of prospective teachers.

There is significant effect of blended learning on the attitude towards educational psychology of prospective teachers.

Conclusion

Through the study it has been found that there is significant effect in positive direction of blended learning on achievement and attitude of prospective teachers towards educational psychology. Blended learning strategy can be considered as one of the new initiatives of pedagogical approaches for integrating ICT in B.Ed. curriculum. In teaching learning process it was found that the students are actively participating in solving the problems. Blended learning provides the opportunities of learning through ICT, online or offline mode so teachers and students get more time in the classroom for creative and cooperative exercise.

It provides the opportunity to the students to express the views of students. Students who are very shy in nature may also participate

in group activities through blended learning and remove their hesitation. Students get face to face interaction as well as they interact in virtual space. Students get ample of time to interact with other students pursuing the same course. Student get full experience in using new technology-the present century is the century of ICT. Today all professionals demand expertise in ICT so blended learning help to make teachers to use ICT their teaching learning process. ICT mediated learning provide students indirect interactions with their course content in a versatile and diverse intersecting way. College campus provides many opportunities for this interaction. Group discussion and exchange of ideas provides students interaction with teachers also well-designed strategies give students to undergo discussion and exchange of ideas. This helps to develops confidence in students. Student can get attach to other experts and enhance his knowledge. Blended learning provides students to gain advantage of the experts of the course content they are studying as they can easily watch the different lectures by renowned experts from different fields available on You Tube. Thus there is a need to use blended learning process in teacher education program as well as try to study its implications for school teaching too.

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